

Institute of Pedagogy of NAES of Ukraine

Department of Monitoring and Evaluation of the
Quality of General Secondary Education

**THE USE OF EDUCATIONAL MONITORING RESULTS
IN TEACHING PRACTICE IN UKRAINIAN SCHOOLS**

Codebook

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2026

The use of educational monitoring results in teaching practice in Ukrainian schools

Codebook

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Abstract: This codebook is intended to support researchers who plan to use survey data collected from school teachers within the study “The use of Educational Monitoring Results in Teaching Practice in Ukrainian Schools”, conducted in 2025–2026. The codebook provides information on all variables included in the Scientific Use File (SUF) and is limited to the documentation of the corresponding dataset.

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Introduction

This codebook has been compiled to provide a systematic description of the dataset generated within a study examining the use of results from educational monitoring studies in the professional practices of teachers at secondary schools in Ukraine. The study was conducted as part of the research project “Methodology for assessing the impact of international and domestic education quality monitoring results on the development of general secondary education in Ukraine” (State Registration Number: 0126U000643).

The data presented in this codebook were collected through a self-administered, structured online survey conducted from November to December 2025. The survey participants were teachers working in general secondary education institutions in Ukraine ($n = 18,851$).

The purpose of this codebook is to ensure a consistent interpretation of the dataset structure, including variable names, response codes, text labels, and missing values, and to establish a unified framework for further descriptive and analytical processing of the study results.

It should be noted that the univariate distributions presented in this codebook are unweighted. Accordingly, they reflect only the distribution of variables within the dataset and do not account for the sampling design or potential biases associated with nonresponse. Readers are therefore strongly advised not to interpret or present these distributions as substantive research findings.

The document specifies the meaning of each variable, the encoding scheme, and the logic for representing responses in the database in the following format:

pedexp – Teaching experience			count	percent
group	value	label		
valid	1	Up to 5 years	1,371	7.38
	2	6–10 years	1,439	7.74
	3	11–20 years	3,248	17.48
	4	21–30 years	3,612	19.44
	5	More than 30 years	5,691	30.63
total			15,361	82.67
missing	NA	Missing value	3,220	17.33
total			18,581	100.00

Figure 1. An example of detailed information about the variable *pedexp*.

1. Variable name.
2. Variable label.
3. Value labels for categories.
4. Absolute frequencies.
5. Percentage distribution.
6. Information on valid responses.
7. Information on missing responses.
8. Information on the total number of responses.
9. Value codes for categories.
10. Information on the total number of valid responses.

1. Structure of the code book

1.1. Variable Naming Convention

Variable names in the dataset are constructed using an abbreviated principle and are oriented toward conciseness, unambiguity, and convenience in subsequent statistical processing. For single categorical variables, short names are used, such as *region*, *settype*, *pedexp*, *age*, *sex*, *educ*, *monexp*, *monitoring*, *teamonexp*, *info_level*, *sourceofinfo*, *teainfo*, *use_blockers*, *realistic_res*, and *effectiveness_res*.

For multiple-response questions, a common variable-name stem and a numerical index are used to indicate a specific response option, for example, *subject_1*, *subject_2*, *edlevel_1*, *forminfo_1*, *useaim_1*, and so on.

Open-ended responses are presented as separate text variables with the suffix *_TEXT*, which makes it possible to distinguish them from coded categorical variables.

1.2. The principle of response coding

Two main approaches were used to code the variables. The first approach applies to single-response variables, in which each category is assigned a distinct numerical code. This approach was used, in particular, for the variables *region*, *settype*, *pedexp*, *age*, *sex*, *educ*, *monexp*, *monitoring*, *teamonexp*, *info_level*, *sourceofinfo*, *teainfo*, *use_blockers*, *realistic_res*, and *effectiveness_res*.

The second approach was applied to multiple-response questions. In this case, each response option is represented as a separate binary variable, where the code 1 indicates that the option was selected, while the code 0 indicates that the option was not selected but was available for selection.

Open-ended responses constitute a separate group of variables. They are not reduced to numerical coding. These variables are intended to record individualized or clarifying responses that cannot be fully represented within a closed set of predefined categories.

1.3. Missing values

In the working version of the dataset, missing values should be treated as standard missing values, coded as NA. This ensures the correct calculation of frequencies, percentages, and summary statistics.

2. List of variables

Variable name	Variable label
<i>Region</i>	Region where the school is located
<i>Subject taught:</i>	
<i>subject_1</i>	Ukrainian language/literature
<i>subject_2</i>	Foreign language
<i>subject_3</i>	Mathematics (algebra, geometry)
<i>subject_4</i>	Biology
<i>subject_5</i>	Physics
<i>subject_6</i>	Chemistry
<i>subject_7</i>	Geography
<i>subject_8</i>	Computer Science
<i>subject_9</i>	History
<i>subject_10</i>	World Literature
<i>subject_11</i>	Vocational Education
<i>subject_12</i>	Physical Education
<i>subject_13</i>	Art / Music
<i>subject_14</i>	Defense of Ukraine
<i>subject_15</i>	Elementary School
<i>subject_16_TEXT</i>	Other (subject taught) – text answer
<i>Grade level:</i>	
<i>edlevel_1</i>	Primary School
<i>edlevel_2</i>	Grades 5–9
<i>edlevel_3</i>	Grades 10–11
<i>settype</i>	Type of settlement where the school is located
<i>pedexp</i>	Teaching experience
<i>age</i>	Respondent's age
<i>sex</i>	Respondent's gender
<i>educ</i>	Respondent's education
<i>monexp</i>	Have students from your school participated in educational quality monitoring studies?
<i>monitoring</i>	In which monitoring studies have students from your school participated?
<i>monitoring_7_TEXT</i>	Other monitoring studies – text response

Variable name	Variable label
<i>teamonexp</i>	Have you personally participated in studies monitoring the quality of education?
<i>info_level</i>	Level of awareness regarding monitoring results
<i>sourceofinfo</i>	Where do you usually find out about the results of the monitoring?
<i>Format of review the monitoring results:</i>	
<i>forminfo_1</i>	News briefs/posts
<i>forminfo_2</i>	Analytical reports
<i>forminfo_3</i>	Presentations/webinars
<i>forminfo_4</i>	Discussions at faculty meetings
<i>forminfo_5_TEXT</i>	Other (format for reviewing monitoring results) – text response
<i>teainfo</i>	Do you receive general, practice-oriented conclusions or recommendations tailored for teachers based on the results of monitoring?
<i>uselevelfreq_ind</i>	Frequency of use of monitoring results at the individual level
<i>uselevelfreq_pedcol</i>	Frequency of use of monitoring results at the level
<i>uselevelfreq_admin</i>	Frequency of use of monitoring results at the administrative level
<i>uselevelfreq_country</i>	Frequency of use of monitoring results at the national level
<i>Purpose of using monitoring results:</i>	
<i>useaim_1</i>	To plan for reviewing topics
<i>useaim_2</i>	To provide individual support to students
<i>useaim_3</i>	To change teaching approaches
<i>useaim_4</i>	To communicate with parents
<i>useaim_5</i>	To evaluate my own work
<i>useaim_6</i>	To improve my professional skills
<i>useaim_7</i>	I do not use it
<i>use_blockers</i>	Barriers to using monitoring results to improve teaching quality
<i>use_blockers_10_TEXT</i>	Other barriers – text response
<i>realistic_res</i>	To what extent do the results of assessments reflect students' actual achievements?
<i>effectiveness_res</i>	How effective are monitoring efforts in improving the quality of education?

Variable name

Variable label

persp_TEXT

In your opinion, how can the results of these assessments be made more useful for teachers?

3. Summary tables

region – The region where the educational institution is located

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	1	Vinnitsia Oblast	424	2.28
	2	Volyn Oblast	912	4.91
	3	Dnipropetrovsk Oblast	1,082	5.82
	4	Donetsk Oblast	2	0.01
	5	Zhytomyr Oblast	326	1.75
	6	Zakarpattia Oblast	7	0.04
	7	Zaporizhzhia Oblast	358	1.93
	8	Ivano-Frankivsk Oblast	521	2.80
	9	Kyiv Oblast	4	0.02
	10	Kyiv City	1	0.01
	11	Kirovohrad Oblast	820	4.41
	12	Luhansk Oblast	1	0.01
	13	Lviv Oblast	698	3.76
	14	Mykolaiv Oblast	774	4.17
	15	Odesa Oblast	2,299	12.37
	16	Poltava Oblast	754	4.06
	17	Rivne Oblast	1,380	7.43
	18	Sumy Oblast	1,568	8.44
	19	Ternopil Oblast	458	2.46
	20	Kharkiv Oblast	1,327	7.14
	21	Kherson Oblast	6	0.03
	22	Khmelnyskyi Oblast	528	2.84
	23	Cherkasy Oblast	640	3.44
	24	Chernihiv Oblast	393	2.12
	25	Chernivtsi Oblast	36	0.19
	total		15,319	82.44
missing	NA	Missing value	3,262	17.56
total			18,581	100.00

subject_1 – Subject taught: Ukrainian Language / Literature

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	13,470	72.49
	1	Response option selected	2,008	10.81

group	value	label	count	percent
	total		15,478	83.30
missing	NA	Missing value	3,103	16.70
total			18,581	100.00

subject_2 – Subject taught: Foreign language

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	13,979	75.23
	1	Response option selected	1,499	8.07
	total		15,478	83.30
missing	NA	Missing value	3,103	16.70
total			18,581	100.00

subject_3 – Subject taught: Mathematics (algebra, geometry)

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	13,917	74.90
	1	Response option selected	1,561	8.40
	total		15,478	83.30
missing	NA	Missing value	3,103	16.70
total			18,581	100.00

subject_4 – Subject taught: Biology

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	14,588	78.51
	1	Response option selected	890	4.79
	total		15,478	83.30
missing	NA	Missing value	3,103	16.70
total			18,581	100.00

subject_5 – Subject taught: Physics

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	14,722	79.23
	1	Response option selected	756	4.07
	total		15,478	83.30
missing	NA	Missing value	3,103	16.70
total			18,581	100.00

subject_6 – Subject taught: Chemistry

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	14,790	79.60
	1	Response option selected	688	3.70
	total		15,478	83.30
missing	NA	Missing value	3,103	16.70
total			18,581	100.00

subject_7 – Subject taught: Geography

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	14,731	79.28
	1	Response option selected	747	4.02
	total		15,478	83.30
missing	NA	Missing value	3,103	16.70
total			18,581	100.00

subject_8 – Subject taught: Informatics

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	14,393	77.46
	1	Response option selected	1,085	5.84
	total		15,478	83.30
missing	NA	Missing value	3,103	16.70
total			18,581	100.00

subject_9 – Subject taught: History

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	14,461	77.83
	1	Response option selected	1,017	5.47
	total		15,478	83.30
missing	NA	Missing value	3,103	16.70
total			18,581	100.00

subject_10 – Subject taught: World Literature

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	14,566	78.39
	1	Response option selected	912	4.91
	total		15,478	83.30
missing	NA	Missing value	3,103	16.70
total			18,581	100.00

subject_11 – Subject taught: Vocational training

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	14,840	79.87
	1	Response option selected	638	3.43
	total		15,478	83.30
missing	NA	Missing value	3,103	16.70
total			18,581	100.00

subject_12 – Subject taught: Physical Education

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	14,743	79.34
	1	Response option selected	735	3.96
	total		15,478	83.30
missing	NA	Missing value	3,103	16.70
total			18,581	100.00

subject_13 – Subject taught: Art/Music

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	14,688	79.05
	1	Response option selected	790	4.25
	total		15,478	83.30
missing	NA	Missing value	3,103	16.70
total			18,581	100.00

subject_14 – Subject taught: Defense of Ukraine

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	15,350	82.61
	1	Response option selected	128	0.69
	total		15,478	83.30
missing	NA	Missing value	3,103	16.70
total			18,581	100.00

subject_15 – Subject taught: Primary School

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	11,908	64.09
	1	Response option selected	3,570	19.21
	total		15,478	83.30
missing	NA	Missing value	3,103	16.70
total			18,581	100.00

subject_16 – Subject taught: Other

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	13,789	74.21
	1	Response option selected	1,689	9.09
	total		15,478	83.30
missing	NA	Missing value	3,103	16.70
total			18,581	100.00

edlevel_1 – Grade level: Primary school

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	9,444	50.83
	1	Response option selected	5,913	31.82
	total		15,357	82.65
missing	NA	Missing value	3,224	17.35
total			18,581	100.00

edlevel_2 – Grade level: 5–9 classes

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	4,640	24.97
	1	Response option selected	10,717	57.68
	total		15,357	82.65
missing	NA	Missing value	3,224	17.35
total			18,581	100.00

edlevel_3 – Grade level: 10–11 classes

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	9,677	52.08
	1	Response option selected	5,680	30.57
	total		15,357	82.65
missing	NA	Missing value	3,224	17.35
total			18,581	100.00

settype – Type of settlement

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	1	City with a population of at least 10,000	5,150	27.72
	2	Settlement with a population of 5,000 or more	1,760	9.47
	3	Village with a population of less than 5,000	8,418	45.30
	total		15,328	82.49
missing	NA	Missing value	3,253	17.51
total			18,581	100.00

pedexp – Teaching experience

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	1	Up to 5 years	1,371	7.38
	2	6–10 years	1,439	7.74
	3	11–20 years	3,248	17.48
	4	21–30 years	3,612	19.44
	5	More than 30 years	5,691	30.63
	total		15,361	82.67
missing	NA	Missing value	3,220	17.33
total			18,581	100.00

age – Age

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	1	18–25	517	2.78
	2	26–35	2,152	11.58
	3	36–45	3,701	19.92
	4	46–55	4,744	25.53
	5	56–65	2,703	14.55
	6	понад 60	1,497	8.06
	total		15,314	82.42
missing	NA	Пропущене значення	3,267	17.58
total			18,581	100.00

sex – Sex

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	1	female	13,622	73.31
	2	male	1,703	9.17
	total		15,325	82.48
missing	NA	Missing value	3,256	17.52
total			18,581	100.00

educ – Education of recipient

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	1	Specialized secondary education	654	3.52
	2	Higher education	14,578	78.46
	3	Academic degree	77	0.41
	total		15,309	82.39
missing	NA	Missing value	3,272	17.61
total			18,581	100.00

monexp – Have students from your school participated in monitoring studies?

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	1	yes	8,492	45.70
	2	no	6,570	35.36
	total		15,062	81.06
missing	NA	Missing value	3,519	18.94
total			18,581	100.00

monitoring – In which monitoring studies has the school participated?

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Other	10,503	56.53
	1	Monitoring of Primary Education Quality	1,504	8.09
	2	Monitoring of the Organization of Distance Learning in General Secondary Education Institutions in the COVID-19 / Wartime Context	1,388	7.47
	3	Nationwide Monitoring Study of Education Quality under Martial Law	1,978	10.65
	4	Monitoring Study of the Implementation of the New Ukrainian School in Primary Education	1,191	6.41
	5	PISA, OECD Programme for International Student Assessment	1,071	5.76
	6	TIMSS, IEA Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study	165	0.89
	7	TALIS, OECD Teaching and Learning International Survey	482	2.59
	total		18,282	98.39
missing	NA	Missing value	299	1.61
total			18,581	100.00

teamonexp – Personal experience participating in monitoring studies

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	1	Yes	5,595	30.11
	2	No	8,793	47.32
	total		14,388	77.43
missing	NA	Missing value	4,193	22.57
total			18,581	100.00

info_level – Level of awareness regarding monitoring results

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	1	Not informed at all	482	2.59
	2	Poorly informed	1,642	8.84
	3	Moderately informed	6,360	34.23
	4	Well informed	4,809	25.88
	5	Very well informed	552	2.97
	total		13,845	74.51
missing	NA	Missing value	4,736	25.49
total			18,581	100.00

sourceofinfo – From where do you usually find out about the results of the monitoring?

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	1	From the school administration	7,073	38.07
	2	From colleagues / methodological association	604	3.25
	3	From professional development courses	1,203	6.47
	4	From official websites, such as the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, the Ukrainian Center for Educational Quality Assessment, and the State Service of Education Quality of Ukraine	2,959	15.92
	5	From educational media	919	4.95
	6	From academic / educational journals	28	0.15
	7	From social media	748	4.03
	8	I do not receive such information	237	1.28
	total		13,771	74.11
missing	NA	Missing value	4,810	25.89
total			18,581	100.00

forminfo_1 – In what format do you usually review the monitoring results?: News briefs/posts

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	8,734	47.01
	1	Response option selected	4,948	26.63
	total		13,682	73.63
missing	NA	Missing value	4,899	26.37
total			18,581	100.00

forminfo_2 – In what format do you usually review monitoring results?: Analytical reports

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	9,308	50.09
	1	Response option selected	4,374	23.54
	total		13,682	73.63
missing	NA	Missing value	4,899	26.37
total			18,581	100.00

forminfo_3 – In what format do you usually review monitoring results?: Presentations/webinars

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	8,273	44.52
	1	Response option selected	5,409	29.11
	total		13,682	73.63
missing	NA	Missing value	4,899	26.37
total			18,581	100.00

forminfo_4 – In what form do you usually review the results of monitoring? : Discussion at faculty meetings

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	5,567	29.96
	1	Response option selected	8,115	43.67
	total		13,682	73.63
missing	NA	Missing value	4,899	26.37
total			18,581	100.00

forminfo_5 – In what form do you usually review the results of monitoring?: Other

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	13,547	72.91
	1	Response option selected	135	0.73
	total		13,682	73.63
missing	NA	Missing value	4,899	26.37
total			18,581	100.00

teainfo – Do you receive practical conclusions/recommendations?

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	1	Yes	9,463	50.93
	2	No	4,085	21.98
	total		13,548	72.91
missing	NA	Missing value	5,033	27.09
total			18,581	100.00

uselevfreq_ind – Frequency of use of results: individual level

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	1	Never	249	1.34
	2	Very rarely	1,664	8.96
	3	Occasionally	5,197	27.97
	4	Often	4,630	24.92
	5	Constantly	1,169	6.29
	total		12,909	69.47
missing	NA	Missing value	5,672	30.53
total			18,581	100.00

uselevfreq_pedcol – Frequency of use of results: level of the teaching staff

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	1	Ніколи	170	0.91
	2	Дуже рідко	1,136	6.11
	3	Епізодично	3,474	18.70
	4	Часто	5,543	29.83
	5	Постійно	2,631	14.16
	total		12,954	69.72
missing	NA	Пропущене значення	5,627	30.28
total			18,581	100.00

uselevfreq_admin – Frequency of use of results: administrative level

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	1	Never	207	1.11
	2	Very rarely	1,027	5.53
	3	Occasionally	3,325	17.89
	4	Often	5,445	29.30
	5	Constantly	2,895	15.58
	total		12,899	69.42
missing	NA	Missing value	5,682	30.58
total			18,581	100.00

uselevfreq_country – Frequency of use: nationwide

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	1	Never	505	2.72
	2	Very rarely	1,754	9.44
	3	Occasionally	4,014	21.60
	4	Often	4,402	23.69
	5	Constantly	2,124	11.43
	total		12,799	68.88
missing	NA	Missing value	5,782	31.12
total			18,581	100.00

useaim_1 – Purpose of using monitoring results: To plan for the review of topics

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	7,606	40.93
	1	Response option selected	5,374	28.92
	total		12,980	69.86
missing	NA	Missing value	5,601	30.14
total			18,581	100.00

useaim_2 – Purpose of using monitoring results: To provide individualized support to students

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	7,640	41.12
	1	Response option selected	5,340	28.74
	total		12,980	69.86
missing	NA	Missing value	5,601	30.14
total			18,581	100.00

useaim_3 – Purpose of using monitoring results: To change teaching approaches

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	5,510	29.65
	1	Response option selected	7,470	40.20
	total		12,980	69.86
missing	NA	Missing value	5,601	30.14
total			18,581	100.00

useaim_4 – Purpose of using the monitoring results: To communicate with parents

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	10,330	55.59
	1	Response option selected	2,650	14.26
	total		12,980	69.86
missing	NA	Missing value	5,601	30.14
total			18,581	100.00

useaim_5 – Purpose of using the monitoring results: For self-assessment of own work

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	6,676	35.93
	1	Response option selected	6,304	33.93
	total		12,980	69.86
missing	NA	Missing value	5,601	30.14
total			18,581	100.00

useaim_6 – Purpose of using the monitoring results: To improve professional skills

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	6,051	32.57
	1	Response option selected	6,929	37.29
	total		12,980	69.86
missing	NA	Missing value	5,601	30.14
total			18,581	100.00

useaim_7 – Purpose of using the monitoring results: I do not use them

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	0	Response option not selected	12,453	67.02
	1	Response option selected	527	2.84
	total		12,980	69.86
missing	NA	Missing value	5,601	30.14
total			18,581	100.00

use_blockers – Blockers of using monitoring results

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	1	Lack of time	4,162	22.40
	2	Insufficient information about monitoring results at the national level	707	3.80
	3	Insufficient information about monitoring results at the school level	330	1.78
	4	The results are too general	1,647	8.86
	5	Lack of practice-oriented information that I can use	1,499	8.07
	6	Complex / unclear presentation of results in reports	467	2.51
	7	Lack of support from the school administration	69	0.37
	8	Insufficient discussion at the level of the school teaching staff	172	0.93
	9	No practical barriers arise	3,717	20.00
	10		117	0.63
	total	Missing value	12,887	69.36
missing	NA	Lack of time	5,694	30.64
total			18,581	100.00

realistic_res – To what extent do the results reflect students’ actual achievements?

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	1	Do not reflect at all	361	1.94
	2	Weakly reflect	1,707	9.19
	3	Partially reflect	5,576	30.01
	4	Mostly reflect	4,159	22.38
	5	Fully reflect	792	4.26
	total		12,595	67.78
missing	NA	Missing value	5,986	32.22
total			18,581	100.00

effectiveness_res – How effective are monitoring efforts in improving the quality of education?

group	value	label	count	percent
valid	1	Not effective at all	544	2.93
	2	Slightly effective	1,801	9.69
	3	Moderately effective	5,836	31.41
	4	Effective	3,918	21.09
	5	Very effective	523	2.81
	total		12,622	67.93
missing	NA	Missing value	5,959	32.07
total			18,581	100.00

subject_16_TEXT – Subject: Other – Text

group	label	n	percent
valid	Text response provided	1,432	7.71
missing	Missing value	17,149	92.29
total		18,581	100.00

monitoring_7_TEXT – Monitoring studies in which the recipients participated (other than those listed in the questionnaire): Other – text

group	label	n	percent
valid	Text response provided	10,719	57.69
missing	Missing value	7,862	42.31
total		18,581	100.00

forminfo_5_TEXT – Form of familiarization with the results: Other – text response

group	label	n	percent
valid	Text response provided	38	0.20
missing	Missing value	18,543	99.80
total		18,581	100.00

use_blockers_10_TEXT – Blockers of using monitoring results in educational practice: Other – text

group	label	n	percent
valid	Text response provided	44	0.24
missing	Missing value	18,537	99.76
total		18,581	100.00

persp_TEXT – How can monitoring results be made more useful for teachers? – open-ended text response

group	label	n	percent
valid	Text response provided	1,627	8.76
missing	Missing value	16,954	91.24
total		18,581	100.00